

Self-standing chitosan film loaded with silver nanoparticles as a tool for selective determination of Cr(VI) by ICP-MS

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ABSTRACT

A fast, simple and sensitive method was developed for separation and speciation of Cr species using dispersive solid phase extraction prior determination by ICP-MS. The selective determination of toxic Cr(VI) in surface waters is achieved after separation of Cr(III) by sorption on self-standing chitosan film loaded with silver nanoparticles (CHS-AgNPs). Completely green synthetic procedure was used for the preparation of AgNPs, which includes D-(+) raffinose as a non-toxic, environmentally benign reducing and capping agent and NaOH as a base reaction catalyst. The raffinose-coated Ag NPs were blended with chitosan to form polyelectrolyte complex that was cast into stable self-standing film. The parameters affecting the extraction efficiency (pH, sorption time, sample volume) of nanocomposite film toward Cr(III) and Cr(VI) were carefully optimized. Effective separation of Cr species between solid and liquid phase is demonstrated by simply tuning the pH value of the sample solution. The analytical method developed is validated under optimized conditions - the detection limit of $0.02 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and determination limit of $0.06 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ were achieved for both Cr

species; the relative standard deviation varied from 3 to 5% for Cr concentrations in the sample solution over the range 0.05-5 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$. The accuracy is established by analysing certified reference materials.

Keywords: Chromium speciation, Solid-phase extraction, Chitosan, Silver nanoparticles, Nanocomposite film, Surface waters

1 Introduction

Chromium is almost ubiquitous in the nature, as ingredient of minerals and rocks and such a component of the most soils, with relatively low natural solubility and bioavailability. Chromium is widely used in the chemical industries, which is mainly responsible for the release of Cr into the surface and ground waters mostly as Cr(III) and Cr(VI) compounds. Chromium (III) is an essential microelement for humans, required for the normal carbohydrate and lipid metabolism. Chromium (VI) compounds are classified as hazardous pollutants due to their high oxidation potential as well as their ability to cross biological membranes. The permissible limits for total Cr content and Cr(VI) concentrations are usually included in the legislation, for quality control of the surface waters, and their determination is a part of the national monitoring programs [1]. Hyphenated analytical methods, which combined chromatographic separation (IC, HPLC) with sensitive detection (ICP-MS), ensured reliable and accurate results for Cr(III) and Cr(VI) content at pristine (background) ng L^{-1} levels in unpolluted surface and ground waters [2-4]. However these methods are expensive and time consuming, therefore simple and rapid nonchromatographic alternatives, the most frequently based on solid phase extraction (SPE) are preferable for routine application [5].

The strategies for inorganic Cr(III)/Cr(VI) speciation could be easily summarized: selective retention of Cr(III), selective retention of Cr(VI) and selective retention of both species all at defined pH values. The next step is elution of sorbed species and instrumental measurement of their concentrations. Serious analytical problem, which has to be taken into account, is preservation of the original concentrations of Cr(III) and Cr(VI) during the transportation of the sample to analytical laboratory. In the recent years, nanomaterials were used as an efficient sorbents for SPE due to their intrinsic properties, such as chemical activity and fine grain size, being better than those of classical substances. In this aspect, metal oxides

(normal-scale titanium dioxide and alumina) sorbents, whose surface has an appropriate charge at the respective pH and provides a high extraction efficiency and selectivity toward Cr species were effectively replaced with their nanosized analogues, in some cases after additional chemical modifications [6-13]. Another nano approach is application of carbon nanotubes, which surface is preliminary functionalized with oxygen containing groups and additionally modified with selective complex forming agents [14-18]. However, the isolation of nanosized sorbents is often laborious and time consuming and thus limits their routine application for dispersive SPE for speciation and determination of trace analytes. On the other side, the practical application of nanosorbents for dynamic SPE might be also restricted due to the high column back pressure. For this reason, nanocomposites, which additionally include magnetic core (Fe_3O_4), are good alternative, allowing these limitations to be overcome, and various nanomaterials were introduced for fast and selective separation and concentration of Cr species by magnetic SPE [19-24]. Chitosan (CHS), which contains reactive functional groups, is a classic sorbent, widely used alone or suitably modified for sorption of Cr(III) or Cr(VI), depending on the experimental parameters, but characterized with a low mechanical and chemical stability [25-28]. In the present study, self-standing films, prepared by the combination of chitosan or polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) as matrices with chemically active pre synthesized AgNPs as crosslinkers, are tested for the first time for dispersive SPE of Cr(III) and selective ICP-MS measurement of Cr(VI) in the supernatant. Completely green synthetic pathway is used for preparation of CHS-AgNPs and PVA-AgNPs nanocomposite films. Simple analytical procedure is developed for separation of Cr(III) and selective determination of toxic Cr(VI) in surface water samples, which avoids desorption steps and might be performed in one reaction vessel, avoiding operations leading to contamination or loss of analyte. The highly sensitive ICP-MS measurement ensures detection and determination limits, which fulfil the requirements for quality control of surface waters. Even more,

dispersive SPE for the retention of Cr(III) on the surface of nanocomposite film might be performed *in situ* along with sampling, thus eliminating any interchanges between Cr species during transportation.

2 Experimental

2.1 Reagents

All reagents used were of analytical-reagent grade and all aqueous solutions were prepared in high-purity water (18.2 M Ω .cm at 25 °C, Millipore Corp., Milford, MA, USA). The stock standard solutions for Cr were: Cr(III), Spex Certiprep 1000 mg L⁻¹ in 2% HNO₃ and Cr(VI) Spex Certiprep 1000 mg L⁻¹ in H₂O. Working standard solutions were prepared daily by appropriate dilution. For validation of the determination of total Cr, Certified Reference Material SLRS-5 River Water reference material for trace metals was used. Additionally, two certified reference materials: Chromium VI in sea water (Fluka® Analytical) and Chromium (VI) – WS (RTC) were used for validation of the analytical procedure developed for Cr(VI) determination.

Analytical grade silver nitrate (AgNO₃, 99.8%, Merck, Germany), D-(+) raffinose pentahydrate (Alfa Aesar, Germany), and sodium hydroxide (NaOH, 99%, Merck, Germany) were used for preparation of aqueous dispersion of silver nanoparticles. Chitosan (low molecular weight, 75–85% deacetylated) and acetic acid (CH₃COOH) were purchased from Sigma–Aldrich, Germany.

2.2 Apparatus

ICP-MS measurements were carried out on a Thermo Scientific, XSeries 2 spectrometer. The optimal instrumental parameters are presented in Table S1 (ESI†). UV-vis absorption spectra were recorded on an Evolution 300 spectrometer (Thermo Scientific, USA). The morphology and particle sizes were examined using a transmission electron microscope (TEM, JEM-2100 operating at accelerating voltage 200 kV). Zeta (ζ) potential was measured with a Zetasizer

Nano ZS (Malvern) instrument. A microprocessor pH-meter (Hanna Instruments, Portugal) was used for pH measurements.

2.3 Nanocomposite film preparation

Completely green chemical procedure were applied for AgNPs synthesis using D-(+) raffinose as non-toxic, environmentally benign reducing and capping agents, and NaOH as a base reaction catalyst (exact procedure is described in Supplementary material). A stock solution of chitosan (1.0% (w/V)) was prepared by dissolving 1 g of chitosan in 100 mL 0.17 mol L⁻¹ CH₃COOH under continuous stirring. A stock PVA solution contains 4 g PVA in 100 mL MilliQ water. Different volumes of aqueous dispersion of AgNPs were blended with fixed volume of chitosan or PVA stock solutions, under magnetic stirring for 15 min, to form homogenous film matrix dispersions with different AgNPs content. Stable transparent self-standing films CHS-AgNPs or PVA-AgNPs were obtained by casting these matrix dispersions on the bottom of 25 mL glass beakers and evaporating the solvent in air atmosphere, at a controlled environment of 50 °C. The CHS-AgNPs films were additionally immersed in 1 mol L⁻¹ NaOH for 1 h in order to neutralize the excess of acetic acid and finally were washed with doubly distilled water until neutral pH.

2.4 Dispersive SPE procedure for Cr(VI) determination

The pH value of model solution, 20 mL MilliQ water containing 1 µg L⁻¹ (C_{initial}) of Cr(III) or Cr(VI), was adjusted to desired value (examined range 7–9, reached by addition of NH₃ solution (10 mol L⁻¹) and was added to the nanocomposite film (CHS-AgNPs or PVA-AgNPs), obtained on the bottom of glass beaker. The sorption process was continued for 1 h without vigorous shaking and the nanocomposite film was carefully removed from the beaker at the end of process. The concentrations (C_{end}) of Cr(III) and Cr(VI) were measured in the solution remained by ICP MS under optimized instrumental parameters.

The degree of sorption (D) was defined as

$$D, \% = (1 - C_{\text{end}}/C_{\text{initial}}) \times 100$$

2.5 Analytical procedure for Cr speciation in surface and ground waters

2.5.1 Sampling procedure. The river samples were sampled according to the ISO 5667-6:2014 (ISO 5667-6:2014), Water quality, Part 6: Guidance on sampling of rivers and streams; the bottled mineral waters were obtained from the market. The sample preservation and handling was according to the ISO 5667-3:2012 (ISO 5667-3:2012), Water quality, Part 3: Preservation and handling of water samples. Briefly, pre-cleaned plastic vessels were used; the water samples (three parallel samples) were filtered through 0.45 μm membrane filters, *on site*, during sampling and acidified with 1 mL 1 mol L⁻¹ HNO₃ per 100 mL sample before transportation to the laboratory.

2.5.2 Determination of total Cr. The total Cr content in the water sample is determined in one run, together with all other elements required for quality control of surface and ground waters, using multielement capabilities of ICP-MS measurement under optimized instrumental parameters.

2.5.3 Determination of Cr(VI). The pH of surface (ground) water sample of 20 mL is adjusted to 8.5 (reached by addition of NH₃, 10 mol L⁻¹) and added to the CHS-AgNPs nanocomposite film, obtained on the bottom of glass beaker. The sorption process was continued for 1 h without vigorous shaking and the nanocomposite film was carefully removed from the beaker at the end of process. The concentration of Cr(VI) in the solution was measured by ICP-MS under the same optimized instrumental parameters such as for the total Cr. Preferably, the procedure for selective determination of Cr(VI) should be performed during sampling, in this way avoiding addition of nitric acid and next pH adjustment with NH₃. Even more, the selective removal of Cr(III) during sampling will ensure reliable determination of Cr(VI) since interconversion between Cr species during transportation is well known fact.

2.5.4 Determination of Cr(III). If necessary, the Cr(III) content could be simply calculated as a difference between both measurements for total Cr and Cr(VI) as far as both measurements were performed under the same instrumental parameters and with equal sensitivity.

2.6 Statistical treatment. For data analysis (statistical differences, Student's test, and analytical figures of merit) the statistical package Statistica 6 was used (StatSoft, Tulsa, OK, USA).

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Film characterization

The nanocomposite films, CHS-AgNPs and PVA-AgNPs, showed a uniform colouring in yellow keeping optical transparency. UV-Vis spectroscopy was used to verify the origin of the observed film optical characteristics from the optical resonant properties of raffinose-coated silver nanoparticles incorporated in chitosan/PVA polymer matrix. The surface plasmon resonance band of AgNPs in the nanocomposite CHS-AgNPs film was located at 444 nm and a red-shift of 33 nm along a strong broadening of the absorption band of AgNPs was observed as shown in Fig. 1 (inset) compared with the SPR band of AgNPs in aqueous dispersion (Fig. S1a (inset) (ESI[†])). Similar results were obtained by Božanić et al. [29], who formed silver-chitosan nanocomposite film by *in-situ* reduction using D-glucose, and where the spectrum of the silver-chitosan nanocomposite film showed a SPR band at 445 nm. In the work by Zeng et al. [30] the UV-Vis spectra of silver nanoparticle-filled composite films with polystyrene and acrylonitrile-styrene copolymer matrices were also recorded and absorption bands at 451 nm and 459 nm, respectively, were obtained. Such effects might be explained as a consequence of the sensitivity of SPR absorption to factors like refractive index of the

environment and space between the neighboring nanoparticles in the film, which affect the intensity of their dipole-dipole coupling [29, 30].

TEM micrograph of CHS-AgNPs nanocomposite film (Fig. 1) proved an unaltered morphology of AgNPs after their immobilization in the chitosan matrix and revealed a uniform distribution of individual raffinose-coated AgNPs in the film. The histogram of size distribution of AgNPs in the film (inset shown on the right side of Fig. 1) showed an average particle diameter of 28.9 ± 8.2 nm, comparable to that of the raffinose-capped silver particles in aqueous dispersion (27.2 ± 6.7 nm; shown in Fig. S1a (inset) (ESI[†])). Similar results were obtained from TEM observation of PVA-AgNPs nanocomposite film (not shown).

The uniformed dispersion of AgNPs within the chitosan and PVA polymer matrices was additionally confirmed by the smooth and homogeneous surface morphology of both nanocomposite films (CHS-AgNPs and PVA-AgNPs), visible in the SEM micrographs (Fig. 2a and 2b). The raffinose-coated AgNPs incorporated into nanocomposite films showed distinctive images (white dots) on the film surface (Fig. 2c and 2d), confirming the good dispersion of AgNPs within the polymer matrices. Similar observations have been reported for alginate-capped AgNPs blended with chitosan and cast into antibacterial composite films [31].

3.2 Optimization of extraction variables for selective sorption of Cr(III) on CHS-AgNPs nanocomposite film

3.2.1 Effect of pH on Cr(III) and Cr(VI) sorption by CHS-AgNPs nanocomposite film.

Sample pH is one of the most important parameters for the selective sorption of Cr species on the sorbent surface. As a weak polybase with pK_a 6.1-6.5, the chitosan shows high affinity to transition metals cations in the range $4 < pH < 8$. The PVA matrix containing OH-groups will be active also at the same pH values. The effect of pH on the retention of Cr(III) and Cr(VI) by CHS-AgNPs/PVA-AgNPs nanocomposite films was studied in the range from 6 to 9 achieved

by $10 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ NH}_3$ (Fig. 3), according to the procedure described in section 2.4. Values of pH below 6 were not studied because of the chitosan capability to retain anions in acidic media. Results depicted in Fig. 3 showed that quantitative sorption of Cr(III) by using CHS-AgNPs nanocomposite film was achieved at pH 8–8.5, while the degree of sorption of Cr(VI) at this pH was below 2%. Both Cr(III) and Cr(VI) were not retained quantitatively on the PVA-AgNPs nanocomposite film (Fig. 3). It could be concluded that the CHS-AgNPs nanocomposite film is a promising sorbent for quantitative and selective separation of Cr(III) and Cr(VI), with very good potential for routine analytical applications. Most probably, the retention of Cr(III) is a combination of electrostatic attraction between the positively charged ammonium complexes of Cr(III) (the predominant chemical species of Cr(III) under the defined experimental conditions) with the negatively charged surface of nanocomposite film (AgNPs with ζ potential of $-47.9 \pm 2 \text{ mV}$) and further complex formation with the deprotonated functional groups of chitosan. Evidently both AgNPs and chitosan are combined synergistically to ensure an efficient sorption of Cr(III), while the negatively charged Cr(VI), which remains in the solution, might be selectively measured by ICP-MS. Even more, the experimental results showed that AgNPs, incorporated in the chitosan matrix, are strongly bonded due to the complex formation with the chitosan functional groups and play additionally a role of crosslinking agent ensuring a high mechanical strength of the nanocomposite film and an easy handling for the analytical applications. The experiments, performed with different amounts of AgNPs between 270 and 1080 $\mu\text{g Ag}$ per film, showed that the optimal Ag content is 540 $\mu\text{g Ag}$ per film. The Cr(III) sorption on nanocomposite films with lower or higher content of AgNPs was below 80%, in the first case due to the lower density of negative charges, and in the second case most probably due to the blocking of chitosan functional groups.

3.2.2 Sorption kinetics. The kinetics of sorption of both Cr(III) and Cr(VI) on the CHS-

AgNPs nanocomposite film was studied for a relatively long time period of 0.5–12 hours at pH 8.5 (procedure in section 2.4). The samples were gently shaken on a shaking machine in order to keep the integrity of nanocomposite film. For comparison, the kinetics of sorption of both Cr(III) and Cr(VI) on the raffinose-coated silver nanoparticles was also studied at the same conditions. As can be seen from the results presented on Fig. 4a, at least one hour is necessary for selective and quantitative sorption of Cr(III) on the surface of the nanocomposite film, while Cr(VI) remains quantitatively in the solution. The quantitative sorption of Cr(III) on the surface of raffinose-coated silver nanoparticles was reached faster (for 25 minutes as seen from Fig. 4b, due to the homogenous distribution of silver nanoparticles in the sample volume compared to CHS-AgNPs nanocomposite film).

3.2.3 Optimal sample volume. Evidently, the degree of sorption of Cr(III) and sorption kinetics depend on the ratio between the nanocomposite film surface and sample volume. The experiments performed with nanocomposite films with different diameters showed that the diameter of 2.5 cm is optimal from view point of the film washing and handling during the sorption. The films with smaller diameters required longer than 1 hour retention times for quantitative sorption of Cr(III), the films with bigger diameters are not enough stable during the washing and are problematic for easy removal from the sample solution. Therefore, the experiments for the influence of sample volume on the degree of sorption of Cr(III) and Cr(VI) were performed with sample volume ranged between 10 and 50 mL using films with 2.5 cm in diameter. The experimental results defined 20 mL as an optimal sample volume ensuring a selective separation of both Cr species for 1 hour sorption time. The adsorption capacity of one nanocomposite film, achieved under these chemical conditions is 10 mmol Cr(III)/per film. This capacity is completely sufficient for retention and separation of Cr(III) even in relatively polluted surface and ground waters.

3.2.4 Film recovery or elution study. The effect of eluent concentration (HNO_3) on the Cr(III) desorption and regeneration of the CHS-AgNPs nanocomposite film was studied at relatively soft conditions from $2 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ HNO}_3$ to $4 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ HNO}_3$, taking into account chemical instability of CHS-AgNPs film in acidic solutions. The results obtained showed that HNO_3 with concentration 2 mol L^{-1} keeps the integrity of nanocomposite film but does not ensure a quantitative elution of Cr(III), which does not allow complete film regeneration for the next sorption cycle. More concentrated HNO_3 ensures complete Cr(III) desorption, however the nanocomposite film is swelled and again is not suitable for next sorption cycle. Consequently, the synthesized CHS-AgNPs nanocomposite film is not recyclable and new one has to be used for each sorption cycle of Cr(III). Taking into account the simple synthesis procedure and the possibilities for simultaneous preparation of significant number of CHS-AgNPs nanocomposite films, this fact just ensures application of fresh sorbent for each sorption cycle and thus reproducible degree of sorption on the fresh film surface.

3.3 Analytical applications

The method was applied for determination of Cr(VI) in real samples. Different types of surface waters and ground waters were spiked with Cr species at varying concentration levels including different ratios of Cr(III) and Cr(VI) and the developed procedure (section 2.5) was applied. The accuracy of method and the matrix effect of real sample on the degree of Cr(III) sorption were assessed by the recovery experiments from prepared spiked samples. The results are presented in Table 1. The recovery values obtained for Cr(VI), independently of the Cr(III)/Cr(VI) ratio, are in the range 92-103% with relative standard deviations (RSD) less than 5%. Moreover, the results demonstrated that the matrices of the real samples had no considerable effect on the determination of Cr(VI) by the proposed analytical procedure, schematically presented in Figure 4. The repeatability of CHS-AgNPs nanocomposite film was investigated by using six different batches prepared independently under identical

experimental conditions from different batches of AgNPs dispersion and CHS solution. The relative standard deviation of degree of sorption in the experiments with $0.1 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ Cr(III) was 4%. The good stability and repeatability of CHS-AgNPs nanocomposite film might be attributed to the simple synthesis procedure, crosslinking properties of AgNPs and sorbent multifunctionality due to the high reactivity of AgNPs and the ability of chitosan to form complexes with Cr. The leakage of Ag in the sample solution during the sorption of Cr(III) by CHS-AgNPs nanocomposite film was less than $1 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for all experiments performed.

3.4 Analytical figures of merit and method validation

The analytical characteristics data related to the performance of developed dispersive SPE for determination of Cr(VI) by using CHS-AgNPs nanocomposite film were defined by 5 parallel analysis of procedural blank (blank run was performed by using 20 mL MilliQ water and CHS-AgNPs nanocomposite film) and 5 parallel analysis of model solutions containing both Cr(III) and Cr(VI) at equal concentration levels of $0.5 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ or $5 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$. The limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ), which depend mainly on the sensitivity of ICP-MS measurements of Cr under the optimized instrumental parameters, were calculated as 3 and 10 times of standard deviation of measured blank values. The results obtained can be summarized as follow: LOD is $0.02 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and LOQ - $0.06 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for both total Cr and Cr(VI). The calculated relative standard deviation varied in the range from 3-5% for the studied concentration range of 0.05 - $5 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ Cr(VI), demonstrating a good precision of the developed analytical procedure.

The accuracy of determination of total Cr content was confirmed by analyzing CRM SLRS-5 (river water). Result obtained coincides very well with certified value (Student t-test, 95% confidence limit). The accuracy of determination of Cr(VI) was verified by analyzing CRM, Chromium VI in sea water (Fluka® Analytical) and CRM Chromium (VI) –WS (RTC). The statistical insignificance for the observed value of $459 \pm 9.8 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for Chromium

VI in sea water (with 95% confidence limit) from the certified value of $450 \pm 13.9 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and $19.3 \pm 0.1 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for Chromium (VI) –WS from the certified value of $19.5 \pm 0.221 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (Student t-test, 95% confidence limit) clearly indicates the absence of systematic errors and confirms the validity of the proposed analytical method for selective determination of Cr(VI) in various matrices without significant interferences. Additionally, the results obtained for Cr(VI) according to the developed analytical procedure were compared with results obtained by on line IC coupled with ICP-MS and very good agreement was found. Comparison of the proposed method with some methods (employing also nanomaterials as sorbents) is presented in Table 1S. Although the direct comparison of enrichment factors and detection limits is often misleading owing to use of different operating conditions, models and instrumental methods, it can be seen, that the proposed analytical method for selective determination of Cr(VI) ensures detection limits, which are better or close to the literature data. Comparison of the proposed method with the analytical procedures, employing the same approach (selective determination of Cr(VI) in the supernatant after Cr(III) sorption) shows, that the present approach is simpler and very easy for handling [7, 32].

4 Conclusions

A simple dispersive SPE extraction procedure is developed for selective determination of Cr(VI), based on preliminary quantitative retention of Cr(III) on chitosan film loaded with silver nanoparticles. Completely green method for the synthesis of nanocomposite film is proposed, the synthesis procedure is with very good repeatability and the films obtained were with high mechanical strength and allowed easy manipulation. The whole analytical procedure for selective Cr(VI) determination is performed in one analytical vessel and is very simple. Any additional operations such as centrifugation/filtration of the sorbent and desorption of the analyte are avoided due to the highly sensitive instrumental method used.

The developed method is environmentally friendly, fast, reproducible and easy to perform. The method was applied to determination of Cr(VI) in surface waters, the method repeatability, LOD and LOQ achieved fulfilled the technical requirements of analytical procedures used in the monitoring programs for the quality control of surface waters. The method could be introduced in the routine analytical practice.

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Figure captions

Figure 1. TEM image of CHS-AgNPs nanocomposite film. The inset on the right side shows the UV–vis spectrum of the same film in comparison with wavelength of SPR plasmon band of Ag NPs in aqueous dispersion. The inset on the left side shows the size distribution histogram of the silver nanoparticles loaded in nanocomposite film.

Figure 2. SEM micrographs of nanocomposite films: **a)** PVA-AgNPs and **b)** CHS-AgNPs. **c)** Polarized optical micrograph and **d)** SEM micrograph with back scattering of CHS-AgNPs nanocomposite film.

Figure 3. The effect of pH on the degree of sorption of Cr(III) and Cr(VI) on CHS-AgNPs and PVA-AgNPs nanocomposite films.

Figure 4. The effect of contact time on the degree of sorption of Cr(III) on: **a)** CHS-AgNPs nanocomposite films and **b)** raffinose-coated AgNPs.

Figure 5. Scheme of analytical procedure for Cr speciation in surface and ground waters by using CHS-AgNPs nanocomposite film.

Table 1

Recovery studies for the determination of Cr(VI) by dispersive SPE and ICP-MS measurements, using CHS-AgNPs nanocomposite film as a selective sorbent for Cr(III) (20 mL sample solution, pH 8.5, 1 h sorption time; three parallel determinations).

Sample	Added Cr(VI) ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)	Found Cr(VI) ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) [mean\pmsd]	Recovery (%)	RSD (%)
River Iskar	0	0.070 \pm 0.002		2
River Iskar	0.1 and 0.1 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ Cr(III)	0.102 \pm 0.008 Cr(VI)	95 \pm 1	3
River Iskar	0.06 and 0.1 $\mu\text{g/L}$ Cr(III)	0.134 \pm 0.005 Cr(VI)	103 \pm 3	3
Mineral water, Beltchin	0	< LOD		
Mineral water, Beltchin	0.1 and 0.2 $\mu\text{g/L}$ Cr(III)	0.102 \pm 0.002	102 \pm 2	2
Mineral water, Beltchin	0.06 and 0.5 $\mu\text{g/L}$ Cr(III)	0.065 \pm 0.012	108 \pm 3	5

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4.

Figure 5.

- Ecofriendly method for synthesis of silver nanoparticles and their incorporation in chitosan nanocomposite...
- Selective sorption of Cr(III) on self-standing chitosan film loaded with silver nanoparticles.
- Simple method for determination of Cr(VI) in surface waters usable in the routine analytical practice.

ELECTRONIC SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Self-standing chitosan film loaded with silver nanoparticles as a tool for selective determination of Cr(VI) by ICP-MS

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Experimental

Table S1 Instrumental parameters for ICP-MS measurements.

Parameters	Option or Setting
Nebulizer	Standard glass concentric
Spray chamber	Standard glass conical impact bead
Sample uptake rate (mL min ⁻¹)	0.5
Cool Gas Flow (L min ⁻¹)	13
Aux. Gas Flow (L min ⁻¹)	0.7
Nebulizer Gas Flow (L min ⁻¹)	0.9
Forward Power (W)	1400
Hexapole Bias (V)	-20
Quadrupole Bias (V)	-17
Cell Gas (He) Flow Rate (mL min ⁻¹)	5.1
Isotope	⁵² Cr

Synthesis of AgNPs

Briefly, 7.5 mL of raffinose solution (0.1 mol L^{-1}) was added to 61.5 mL of AgNO_3 ($1.2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$) solution and homogenized in ultrasonic environment for 15 min, followed by the addition of 4 mL of NaOH solution (0.1 mol L^{-1}). The reaction mixture was kept in ultrasonic environment for 60 min at $30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. A change of the solution colour from colourless to pale brown and subsequently to yellow orange was indication of AgNPs formation.

Characterization of AgNPs by UV-Vis spectroscopy, TEM/SAED and XRD analyses, and DLS measurements

The UV-Vis absorption spectrum of yellow orange solution of raffinose-stabilized AgNPs showed a strong surface plasmon resonance (SPR) band at 411 nm (inset in Fig. S1a). The shape of the plasmon band is symmetrical and quite narrow, confirming that AgNPs are mainly spherical with narrow size distribution. A clear evidence of the high colloidal stability of the same nanoparticles in aqueous dispersion is the reproducibility of UV-vis spectrum of silver nanoparticles measured at various storage periods. The high colloidal stability of raffinose-stabilized AgNPs was additionally confirmed by the ζ potential value of $-47.2 \pm 1.1 \text{ mV}$ measured in 1 mmol L^{-1} KCl at pH 6.8. The exact size, particle size distribution, and morphology of raffinose-coated silver nanoparticles were characterized by TEM observations, shown in Fig. S1a. The TEM micrograph shows quasi-spherical silver nanoparticles with narrow size distribution revealed by the size distribution histogram (inset in Fig. S1a). In addition to the nanospheres, some typical polyhedral nanoparticles (multiple twined nanocrystals) can be easily observed. The average particle diameter estimated from TEM images is $27.2 \pm 6.7 \text{ nm}$. This result is in a good accordance with the average hydrodynamic diameter ($34.5 \pm 0.9 \text{ nm}$) of

raffinose-coated silver nanoparticles obtained by DLS measurements (Fig. S1b). As expected, the hydrodynamic diameter of raffinose-coated silver nanoparticles has higher value than that of the metal core of nanoparticles obtained by TEM observations. The HRTEM micrograph on the bottom of Fig. S1a revealed the crystal nature of raffinose-coated silver nanoparticles.

Figure S1. a) TEM image of the raffinose-coated silver nanoparticles; the inset on the right side and on the bottom show the UV–vis spectra of the same nanoparticles at various storage periods and HRTEM micrograph, respectively; the inset on the left side shows the size distribution histogram of the nanoparticles. b) Size distribution histogram of the raffinose-coated silver nanoparticles obtained by DLS measurements.

The selected area electron diffraction pattern (SAED) and X-ray diffraction (XRD) pattern of green synthesized raffinose-coated AgNPs are shown in Fig. S2.

Figure S2. XRD pattern of synthesized raffinose-stabilized silver nanoparticles; the inset shows the SAED pattern of the same nanoparticles.

The SAED pattern (inset in Fig. S2) exhibits a bright circular rings corresponding to the (111), (200), (220), (311), and (222) planes, which confirms the polycrystalline nature of the synthesized AgNPs. The XRD pattern of raffinose-stabilized AgNPs (Fig. S2) showed four broad

diffraction peaks with weak intensity at 2Θ of 38.2° , 44.4° , 64.6° and 77.4° , corresponding to the diffraction planes (111), (200), (220) and (311) of the face-centered cubic (fcc) silver (PDF 04-0783), confirmed by SAED pattern and HRTEM observation. No impurity peaks were observed in the X-ray diffraction pattern of raffinose-stabilized AgNPs. The XRD pattern of dried AgNPs layer did not exhibit any characteristic diffraction peaks of raffinose. This could be a result of the partial degradation of the raffinose in the alkaline conditions of nanoparticle synthesis [1] and the formation of non-crystalline complexes of raffinose with the nanoparticles, as well [2].

Table S2

Strategies and sorbents for Cr(III)/Cr(VI) speciation.

Species	Sorbent	Instrumental method	Sample	Detection limit, $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$	Ref.
Cr(III) Cr(VI)	Nanometer-sized TiO_2 microcolumn	ICP-OES	Water	0.32 Cr(III)	[3]
Cr(III) Cr(VI)	Nanometer-sized TiO_2 immobilized on silica gel	ICP-OES	Water	0.22 Cr(III)	[4]
Cr(III) Cr(VI)	Nanometer-sized TiO_2	FI ETAAS	Drinking water	0.01 Cr(VI) 0.006 Cr(III)	[5]
Cr(III)	Mercaptoundecanoic acid modified TiO_2 core–Au shell nanoparticles	Slurry ETAAS	Sea water Drinking water	0.34	[6]
Cr(III) Cr(VI)	TiO_2 nanotubes	ICP-MS	Water	0.23 Cr(III)	[7]
Cr(III) Cr(VI)	Nano-Ba-Sr titanate	FAAS	Water		[8]
Cr(III) Cr(VI)	Amine-functionalized bimodal mesoporous silica nanoparticles	FAAS	Water	1.2 Cr(VI)	[9]
Cr(III) Cr(VI)	Knotted reactor with magnetically immobilized amine-functionalized Fe_3O_4 microspheres	ICP-MS	Drinking water	1.5 ng L^{-1} Cr(III) 2.1 ng L^{-1} Cr(VI)	[10]
Cr(III) Cr(VI)	$\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4@Zr\text{O}_2$	FAAS	Environmental samples	0.69 Cr(III)	[11]

			Biological samples		
Cr(III) Cr(VI)	Fe ₃ O ₄ @Al ₂ O ₃	FAAS	Water Waste water	0.083 Cr(VI)	[12]
Cr(III) Cr(VI)	Zincon-immobilized silica-coated Fe ₃ O ₄	ETAAS	Water	0.016 Cr (III) 0.011 Cr(VI)	[13]
Cr(III) Cr(VI)	Fe ₃ O ₄ @Al ₂ O ₃ modified by surfactant Triton X-114	FAAS	Water Soil	1.4-3.6 Cr(III) for waters 5.6 for soil	[14]
Cr(III) Cr(VI)	Chitosan-modified Fe ₃ O ₄ nanoparticles	ICP-OES	Waters	0.02 Cr(III) 0.03 total Cr	[15]
Cr(III) Cr(VI)	Mesoporous amin-functionalized Fe ₃ O ₄ (dispersive MSPE combined with CPE)	FAAS	Water Biological samples	1.1 Cr(VI) 3.2 Cr(III)	[16]
Cr(VI) Cr(III)	Graphene oxide, decorated with magnetite modified with triethylenetetramine	FAAS	Tannery waste water River water Industry water	1.4 Cr(V) 1.6 Cr(III)	[17]
Cr(III)	MWCNTs, oxidized with conc. HNO ₃	FAAS	Natural water	1.15 Cr(III)	[18]
Cr(III)	MWCNTs, impregnated with D2EHPA	ICP AES	Tap and well water Industrial waste water	0.05	[19]
Cr(VI)	MWCNTs, APDC	FAAS	River water Waste and tannery water	0.9	[20]
Cr(III) Cr(VI)	SWCNTs, oxidized	ICP-MS	Natural water Waste waters	0.01 Cr(III) 0.024 Cr(VI)	[21]
Cr(III) Cr(VI)	poly N-(4-bromophenyl)-2-methacryl-mide-co-2-acrylamido-2-methyl-1-propanesulfonic acid-co-divinylbenzeneP-3	FAAS	Tap water Lake water Spring water Wastewater	1.58 Cr(III)	[22]
Cr(III) Cr(VI)	poly(N,N'-dipropionitrile methacrylamide-co-divinylbenzene-co-2-acrylamido-2-methyl-1-propanesulfonic acid)	FAAS	Spiked water Food samples	1.11 Cr(III)	[23]
Cr(III) Cr(VI)	β-Cyclodextrin cross-linked polymer	ETAAS	Environmental waters	0.056 Cr(III)	[24]
Cr(III) Cr(VI)	Poly(1,3-thiazol-2-yl methacrylamide-co-4-vinyl pyridine-co-divinylbenzene)	FAAS	Stream water, Wastewater	2.4 Cr(VI)	[25]
Cr(III)	Poly(methacrylic acid) and	FAAS	Tap water	0.84 Cr(III)	[26]

Cr(VI)	poly(vinylimidazole) cross-linked with ethylene glycol dimethacrylate		Mineral water Lake water	2.81 Cr(VI)	
Cr(III) Cr(VI)	Poly 2-(5-methylisoxazol) methacrylamide-co-2-acrylamido-2-methyl-1-propanesulfonic acid-co-divinyl-benzene and Dowex 21K resin	FAAS	Tap water Seawater Spring water Industrial water	0.05 Cr(III) 0.3 Cr(VI)	[27]
Cr(III) Cr(VI)	Cr(III)-pyrrolidinedithiocarbamate complex/acrylamide/ethylene glycol dimethacrylate	ETAAS	Tap and river water Municipal sewage	0.018 Cr(III)	[28]
Cr(III) Cr(VI)	Cr(III)-8-hydroxyquinoline/styrene / divinylbenzene	FAAS	CRM of waste water	2.1 Cr(III)	[29]
Cr(III) Cr(VI)	Cr(III)/3-(2-aminoethylamino) propyltrimethoxysilane (on silica gel)	ICP-MS	ICP-MS	4.43 ng L ⁻¹ Cr(III)	[30]
Cr(III) Cr(VI)	Cr(III)/3-aminopropyl-triethoxysilane on SBA-15	ICP-AES and UV-vis	Plating and leather wastewater	0.53 Cr(III)	[31]
Cr(III), Cr(VI)	Cr(III)/3-aminopropyl-triethoxysilane/tetraethyl-orthosilicate on silica gel	ICP-AES	Lake water Tap water	0.11 Cr(III)	[32]
Cr(III) Total Cr	Ag-NPs CPE by Triton X-114	ETAAS	Water Beer; Wine	0.002 Cr(III)	[33]
Cr(III)	Dowex Optipore L493 modified with dithizone	FAAS	Industrial waters	0.13	[34]
Cr(III) Cr(VI)	Amberlite XAD-1180 resin	FAAS	Water; Food, Pharmaceuticals	7.7 Cr(VI) 8.6 total Cr	[35]
Cr(III) Cr(VI)	Polystyrene divinylbenzene copolymer as a chelating resin	ETAAS	Wastewater	0.6 Cr(III) 0.9 Cr(VI)	[36]
Cr(VI)	Clay mineral montmorillonite saturated with potassium ions (MTK)	ICP-OES	Water effluents	0.2	[37]
Cr(VI)	chitosan-AgNPs nanocomposite film	ICP-MS	Surface waters	0.02	This work

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